

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF FORMING STUDENTS' COGNITIVE COMPETENCE WITH THE HELP OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. This article discusses about some pedagogical aspects of forming students' cognitive competence with the help of innovative technologies and here is given some ways and their analyzes.

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In any professional field, you use cognitive skills to solve problems in the workplace and improve the quality of your work. Displaying cognitive skills both in an interview and on your resume can also make you a more appealing job candidate. You develop cognitive skills throughout your life, but strategically improving them can help you better use these abilities in the workplace. In this article, we will define cognitive skills, provide examples and explore how you can improve your own cognitive abilities. Cognitive skills, or cognitive abilities, are the ways that your brain remembers, reasons, holds attention, solves problems, thinks, reads and learns. Your cognitive abilities help you process new information by taking that information and distributing it into the appropriate areas in your brain. When you need that information later, your brain also uses cognitive skills to retrieve and use that information. By developing cognitive skills, you help your brain complete this process more quickly and efficiently, and you ensure that you understand and effectively process that new information. In the workplace, cognitive skills help you interpret data, remember team goals, pay attention during an important meeting and more. These skills help you recall previous information that may relate to your organization's goals and help you make important connections between old and new information so you work more effectively.

Cognitive ability, also called cognitive skills, refers to naturally occurring skills of the brain used for both simple and complex tasks. Cognitive skills relate to how an individual processes information, recognizes patterns and analyzes problems. These skills can be honed by focusing on areas that need improvement. While you might have strengths in some cognitive abilities, there's always room for self-improvement. The human brain's ability to learn and evolve means you can always progress a cognitive skill that may not be as strong as others.

Brain is a vital organ of our body. It's the reason why we move, eat, write, talk, and more. Practically everything we do is because our brain sends signals through the nervous system to other body parts. Similarly, the brain needs sharpened cognitive skills to focus, learn, think, remember details, and eventually solve problems effectively. To score high marks and ace exams effectively, all the cognitive needs of students should be met. So, how to improve cognitive skills in students? The answer is to engage them in physical activities, tickle their curiosity, use brain training games in classrooms, nurture their creativity, and introduce them to new skills and experience. Let us learn more in detail:

Engage Learners in Physical Activities

Research has proven that exercise has positive effects on memory function. Those who engage in daily physical activities, their cognitive function improves significantly. The primary reason being that physical activities test your quick thinking and decision making skills. As a teacher, ask your students to do some form of physical activity or a quick warmup before the class. This will keep their minds stimulated during the lectures. Thus, fulfilling the cognitive needs of students.

Tickle Students Curiosity

The answer to your question on how to improve cognitive skills in students is by keeping learners curious. It's a known fact that children who participate in reading books, writing and engaging in brain-stimulating activities at any age have better cognitive development than others. During lectures you can promote brain-

stimulating techniques that will tickle their curious minds. Thus, improving the cognitive skills of students.

Use Brain Training Games in Classrooms

Games are always considered as the best possible way to improve the cognitive skills of students. They promote learners to think quickly, analyze fast and make a decision within an instance. As an educator, you can use this to your advantage and conduct in-class gaming activities. This will not only aid in making learning fun but will also satisfy the cognitive needs of students.

Nurture Students Creativity

A creative task pushes students to think outside the box and come up with something unique. This allows learners to explore new sides of themselves. Arts and crafts classes do the trick in schools. They promote creativity by letting children tap into their minds and bring their imagination to life.

Introduce Students to New Skills and Experience

A unique way to answer your question of how to improve cognitive skills in students is by introducing learners to new skills. Adapting to the new-age skill set while networking socially simultaneously allows learners to stay witty and sharp. It's important to ask your students to step out of their comfort zones and do something that is mentally challenging and unfamiliar. This also plays a prominent role in improving your students' personality traits.

By using these practices, you can help learners carve a better personality. Thus, making them ready for all the challenges that might come their way in the future. These practices also answer your everlasting question of how to improve cognitive skills in students. Moreover, if you want to conduct lectures and teach students how to improve their cognitive skills, then opt for the SuperTeacher teaching platform. It allows you to go digital and kickstart live classes within minutes.

Used literature:

1. Kiely, Kim (2014). "Cognitive function". In Michalos, Kim M. (ed.). *Encyclopedia of Quality of Life and Well-Being Research*. Springer. pp. 974–978.
2. Goel, Vinod (2007). "Anatomy of deductive reasoning". *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*. P. 435–441.
3. Schwarz-Friesel, Monika (2012). "On the status of external evidence in the theories of cognitive linguistics". *Language Sciences*. 34 (6): 656–664.
4. Lakoff, George (2012). "Explaining Embodied Cognition Results". *Topics in Cognitive Science*. 4 (4): 773–785.
5. Blomberg O (2011). "Concepts of cognition for cognitive engineering". [International Journal of Aviation Psychology](#). 21 (1): 85–104.
6. Komilova, N. A. (2022, June). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL VERBALIZERS OF THE CONCEPT "GENDER" IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES. In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences* (pp. 103-106).
7. Komilova, N. A. Comparative Analysis of "Gender" Concept and Issues of Gender Field in English and Uzbek Languages.
8. Do'smatov, H. (2022, June). O 'ZBEK TILIDA SO 'Z TURKUMLARI TASNIFI MASALALARI. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 108-113).
9. Abdilkadimovna, K. N. (2021). Comparative And Linguocultural Analysis Of The Concept" Gender" In Uzbek And English Languages. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(06), 112-117.
10. Мирзаахмедович, Х. Ф., & Комилова, Н. А. (2021). ИНГЛИЗ ВА ЎЗБЕК ТИЛЛАРИДА ГЕНДЕР КОНЦЕПТУАЛ СЕМАНТИКАСИ ВЕРБАЛИЗАТОРЛАРИ НОМИНАТИВ ТУРЛАРИНИНГ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 4(6).

11. qizi, S. G. N. ., & qizi, R. M. A. . (2022). Word Categories in English. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 26, 14-16. Retrieved from <https://cejsr.academicjournal.io/index.php/journal/article/view/1431>
12. Shodieva, G. N. Q., & Rakhmonova, M. A. Q. (2021). INFORMATION PERIOD CHANGE OF PEOPLE'S OUTLOOK, NEGATIVE AND POSITIVE IMPACT OF THE INTERNET. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 563-566.
13. Do'smatov, D., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2022, May). O 'ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDA SO 'ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH TAMOYILLARI. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING* (Vol. 1, No. 8, pp. 770-774).
14. Shodiyeva, G. N. Q. (2022). MATN GRAMMATIKASINING ASOSIY MUAMMOLARI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(NUU Conference 2), 1173-1176.
15. Kizi, S. G. N., & Tolibovna, S. A. (2022). Semantic features and new methods of non-standard English. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 24(17), 2-272.
16. Najmiddinovna, R. Z., & Najmiddinovna, R. K. (2022). INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(05), 19-21.
17. Usmanova, D., & kizi Shodieva, G. N. ISSUES OF CLASSIFICATION OF WORD CATAGORIES IN THE UZBEK.
18. Qizi, S. G. N. (2022). ISSUES OF CLASSIFICATION OF WORD CATAGORIES IN THE UZBEK. *Science and innovation*, 1(B3), 812-816.

Internet resources

1. www.edu.uz
2. www.mygov.uz

3. www.library.com
4. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cognition>